

ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBE/NAFION NANOCOMPOSITE IONIC ELECTROACTIVE POLYMER ACTUATORS

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1 Introduction

Ionic electroactive polymers (*i*-EAPs) are attractive because relatively large electromechanical actuations can be generated under low voltage (~ a few volts) [1-6]. Hence, they can be directly integrated with microelectronic controlling circuits, which have operation voltage of several volts, to perform complex actuation functions and low applied voltage also makes them safe to use. These *i*-EAP actuators hold promise for applications including artificial muscles, robots, micro-electromechanical systems (MEMS) and nano-electromechanical systems (NEMS), and energy harvesting. A critical issue in applying the *i*-EAPs for these applications is how to significantly improve the electromechanical performance, including the actuation speed, actuation strain level and efficiency.

Recent advances in fabricating controlled-morphology aligned carbon nanotube (VA-CNTs) with ultra-high volume fraction create unique opportunities for markedly improving the electromechanical performance of ionic polymer conductor network composite actuators (IPCNCs). The experimental results show that the continuous paths through inter-VA-CNT channels for fast ion transport and low electrical conduction resistance due to the continuous CNTs in the composite electrodes of the IPCNC lead to fast actuation speed (>10% strain/second).[7] A design challenge in developing advanced actuator materials is how to suppress or eliminate unwanted strains generated under electric stimulation, which reduce the actuation efficiency and may also lower the actuation strains. The experimental results demonstrate that the VA-CNTs create non-isotropic elastic modulus in the composite electrodes which suppresses the unwanted strain and markedly

enhances the actuation strain (>8% strain under 4 volts). The data here show the promise of optimizing the electrode morphology in IPCNCs via the ultra-high volume fraction VA-CNTs for ionic polymer actuators to achieve high performance. The low operation voltage, high strain level, and fast actuation speed make the IPCNCs with ultra-high volume fraction VA-CNTs suitable for applications such as artificial muscles, robots, micro-electromechanical devices, and even PEM fuel cells [7]. A transmission line model will be shown to aid in understanding how the ions interact within the actuator based on observed resistive and capacitive behavior in the experimental impedance spectra.

2 Experimental

2.1 VA-CNTs fabrication

VA-CNTs were grown using a modified chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method on silicon substrates using an Fe-on-alumina catalyst system. The resulting aligned CNTs have been characterized previously for alignment, CNT diameter, distribution, and spacing. By varying the inter-tube distance via mechanical densification, variable densities can be obtained [8].

2.2 Composite Fabrication

In the fabrication process of the VA-CNT forest/Nafion composites, the alcohol solvent in a commercial Nafion dispersion purchased from Ion-Power was replaced by dimethylformamide (DMF). The DMF/Nafion solution is infiltrated into CNT arrays under vacuum for several hours to remove any trapped air. After removing the solvent, the composite is annealed at 130 °C under vacuum for 1h to increase crystallinity of the Nafion. The fabricated VA-CNTs/Nafion nanocomposites were embedded in an epoxy and then sectioned using a

finesse microtome with VA-CNTs perpendicular to the cutting direction. Excess epoxy at the edges was removed by manually trimming the edges with a razor blade.

2.3 Actuator Fabrication

The VA-CNT/Nafion CNC layers were bonded to the Nafion film by an ultrathin layer of Nafion dispersion ($< 0.1 \mu\text{m}$), which was deposited on the neat Nafion film surfaces by ultrasonic spraying. CNC layers were laminated on the neat Nafion film surfaces and the CNC/Nafion/CNC actuator stack was then clamped by two Kapton films under pressure. The stacks were dried and then annealed at 130°C to further improve the bonding. 40wt% of 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate (EMI-Tf) is soaked into the actuator. 50 nm thick gold electrodes are bonded on composite surfaces to increase surface conductivity. The fabricated actuator is shown in Fig. 2. (a) and (b).

3 Results and Discussion

For the bending actuators investigated here, the strains generated in the two electrodes have the same magnitude with opposite sign. As a result, the anisotropic strain generation property of the VA-CNT/Nafion composite could not be easily measured. Hence, this unique property is demonstrated by directly measuring the strains generated along and perpendicular to the CNT alignment direction (i.e., the thickness direction or z-direction) of VA-CNTs/Nafion composites from the absorption of Imidazolium ionic liquids (ILs). For the comparison, pure Nafion films were also fabricated under the same condition and the strains due to the absorption of ILs were also characterized along and perpendicular to the thickness direction. Imidazolium based IL, EMI-Tf, was chosen for the study in this paper.

After soaking with IL, the CNCs filled with VA-CNTs exhibit a very different anisotropic deformation from the Nafion films. The pure Nafion films, upon absorption of EMI-Tf, exhibit a large thickness strain and a much smaller lateral strain. In contrast, the VA-CNTs/Nafion nanocomposite films exhibit much smaller thickness strain, while the lateral strain is enhanced. These results demonstrate that the high volume fraction VA-CNTs reduce the strain in the composites along its alignment direction

while enhancing the strain in the perpendicular direction, both characteristics highly desirable for the actuators developed here.

The ionic actuators developed with CNT/Nafion composites exhibit an actuation strain of more than 8% under 4 volts with fast actuation speed $\tau=0.82\text{s}$, as shown in Fig. 2. (a) and (b). The strain level and actuation speed of the ionic polymer actuators developed here are much improved compared with that of the bimorph actuators with $\text{RuO}_2/\text{Nafion}$ CNC electrodes, which have been investigated extensively and have shown the highest strain response (3% strain) among the IPCNC actuators studied earlier. [9, 10]

To understand the interaction between ions and electrodes in VA-CNTs/Nafion based bending actuators, a transmission line model is employed to analyze the impedance of the actuators. To illustrate the physical meaning of each component and minimize the fitting parameters, the complicated de Levie transmission line model [11] in Fig. 4(a) for composites is simplified into a capacitors and resistors network in Fig. 4(b). Since this device has two phases (electrical conductor phase and ionic conductor phase), with resistance within each phase and capacitances between the two phases. C_1 is the interface resistance between the ionic liquids in CNC layer and the gold external electrodes; C_2 represents the capacitance between ionic liquids in CNC layer and the electrical conductor (CNTs) in the CNC layer; C_3 and C_4 are the interface capacitance between the electrical conductor (CNTs) and the ionic liquids in the ionomer layer (Nafion). For the conduction of ionic liquids, three resistances represent, respectively, the ionic resistance in the composite (R_1), on the interface (R_2) and in the bulk Nafion middle layer (R). The resistance of the highly conductive CNTs is neglected. The data and fitting are shown in Fig. 4(c) and the fitting parameters are summarized as follows for the device studied: $C_1=40\mu\text{F}$, $C_2=80\mu\text{F}$, $C_3=16\mu\text{F}$, $C_4=3\mu\text{F}$, $R_1=3\text{k}\Omega$, $R_2=500\Omega$ and $R=617\Omega$. It can be seen that the model fits the experimental data quite well.

4 Conclusions

In conclusion, we show that the ionic polymer nanocomposite actuators with VA-CNTs/Nafion electrodes of controlled morphology exhibit three distinct advantages compared to the traditional ionic polymer actuators with the CNCs with randomly

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dispersed conductor nanoparticles: providing continuous ionic conduction paths through inter-VA-CNT channels, eliminating the electric current resistance due to the continuous CNTs, and creating desired elastic anisotropy to enhance the strain along the actuation direction. The results also demonstrate that the controlled morphology ionic polymer nanocomposites can optimize electroactive device performance in strain (8%) and speed (0.82s time constant) by allowing new tailoring opportunities which are attractive for applications in sensors and actuators, energy harvesting, and even PEM fuel cells. A transmission line model has also been developed to understand how the ions interact within the actuator based on observed resistive and capacitive behavior in the experimental impedance spectra.

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Fig.1. Schematics of a) a CNC/ionomer/CNC three-layer bimorph actuator with VA-CNTs in the CNC layers b) Bending mechanism of Nafion/VA-CNTs CNC composite actuator

Fig.2. SEM of a) a CNC/ionomer/CNC three-layer bimorph actuator. b) Nafion/VA-CNTs CNC composite [7].

Fig 3. a) Optical image of the actuation of the IPCNC under 4 V. b) Normalized strain versus time fitting to determine the time constant $\tau=0.82\text{s}$ [7].

Fig.4. (a) De Levie Transmission line model. (b) simplified transmission line model for CNT/Nafion composite actuators. (c) Experimental impedance data and the fitting from transmission line model.

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